

FACTORS AFFECTING THE PSYCHOLOGY OF STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF STUDYING AT A UNIVERSITY

Vokhsidova Khusnora Murodullaevna

Karshi State University, Faculty of Physics and Mathematics,
Department of Physics, 4th year
E-mail: koraleva_rnb@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5514934>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 05th September 2021
Accepted: 10th September 2021
Online: 15th September 2021

KEY WORDS

learning activity, learning success, academic performance, motivational and personal qualities, self-regulatory qualities.

Many factors influence the success of students' education in higher educational institutions: financial situation; health status; age; marital status; the level of pre-university training; possession of the skills of self-organization, planning and control of their activities (primarily educational); motives for choosing a university; the adequacy of the initial ideas about the specifics of university education; form of study (full-time, evening, part-time, distance learning, etc.); availability of tuition fees and its value; organization of the educational process at the university; material base of the university; the level of qualifications of teachers and service personnel; the prestige of the university and, finally, the individual psychological characteristics of students. This article is devoted to the analysis of these features, methods of assessing and taking them into

ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the success of education at the university. The essence of the concepts "learning activity", "learning success", "academic performance" is revealed, the structure of educational success in the process of education at a university is presented. The analysis of scientific research devoted to the identification of psychological factors influencing the success of students' education in higher educational institutions is carried out. The role of motivational-personal and self-regulatory qualities of students in achieving success in university studies is shown.

account in order to increase the effectiveness of the educational process. Why do some students work hard and willingly on mastering knowledge and professional skills, and the difficulties that arise only add energy and desire to achieve their goal, while others do everything as if from under a stick, and the appearance of any significant obstacles dramatically reduces them activity up to the destruction of learning activity? Such differences can be observed under the same external conditions of educational activity (socio-economic situation, organization and methodological support of the educational process, teacher qualifications, etc.). When explaining this phenomenon, psychologists and teachers most often appeal to such individual psychological characteristics of students as the level of intelligence (the ability to assimilate knowledge, abilities,

skills and successfully apply them to solve problems); creativity (the ability to develop new knowledge yourself); educational motivation, providing strong positive experiences in achieving educational goals; high self-esteem, leading to the formation of a high level of aspirations, and others in conditions of fairly frequent or long-term failures that are inevitable in any complex activity. Each teacher can give examples from his teaching practice, when a very capable and creative student with high (and sometimes inadequately high) self-esteem and initially strong learning motivation, "broke down", faced with serious difficulties in one or another type of learning activity and stopped moving forward, while his much less gifted comrade successfully overcame these difficulties and, over time, achieved much more.

To come to the answer to this question, it is necessary at least briefly to consider the main types of psychological and psychophysiological characteristics of people, as well as the available data on their influence on the educational activity of students.

Currently on the agenda is the question of stage-by-stage coordination of the transition of the process of military education to a credit-modular system. Foreign experience in organizing the educational process shows that the methods and forms of education used in universities are those that have achieved the intended results aimed at creating an environment that will motivate the student himself to receive an education. In our higher educational institution, we also consider it correct to gradually begin the transfer of the educational process of military education faculties to a credit-

modular system. The fact is that military training consists of theoretical, practical, visual, tactical, tactical and control forms, most of which are of a practical nature and are carried out in accordance with the requirements of the charter of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the organization and conduct of firearms training, instructions and instructions on work with military weapons, as well as strict observance of the requirements of the charter of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Theoretical knowledge is strengthened and controlled by exercises, actions and actions performed in combat training in the field. Due to the nature of military education, some officer-teachers prefer not to abandon traditional methods of military education, emphasizing that there is no need to transfer military education to a credit-modular system, but this idea cannot be justified in the current accelerated development. Because the further development of military education as a form of training, both methodological and technological, remains a requirement of the time. The modular education system was first officially mentioned in 1972 at the UNESCO World Conference in Tokyo. Modular learning technology is a derivative of the general theory of functional systems, neurophysiology of thinking, pedagogy and psychology. According to research in these areas, the human brain, composed of tissue modules, receives information best in quantum form (in other words, in the form of known contributions). Modular training provides opportunities for a comprehensive solution to the following modern issues of vocational education

- module - optimization and systematization of training content based

on a functional approach to ensure flexibility and flexibility of programs;

- individualization of training;

- monitoring the effectiveness of training at the level of practical training and assessment of the observed actions;

Activation of the learning process based on professional motivation (interest), independence and full realization of learning opportunities. In the modern theory and practice of modular learning, two different approaches can be distinguished: an activity-based approach

based on science, and a pedagogical technology based on a systematic activity approach. The modular teaching technology is developed and implemented in accordance with the accepted teaching principles. Information about the methods and technologies used in military education is also available in the textbook. The question is what kind of military science and what subject an officer-teacher can choose and apply in his place. In this regard, the degree to which the facilitator has mastered a modern approach to teaching is also of great importance.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Ishkov A.D. Student educational activity: psychological factors of success. Moscow: ASV Publishing House, 2004. 224 p.
2. Smirnov S.D. Psychological factors of successful studies of university students URL: <http://www.psy.msu.ru/science/public/smirnov/students.html>